

THE ROLE OF ICT IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRE-SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

This article is dedicated to find the place of contemporary technologies in teaching English language in preschool. There are heaps of strategies and approaches in teaching method. There'll be an ancient manner as everything is that the same. While not innovative technologies, the teaching system might not be flourished. The fundamental blessings of victimisation these tools in teaching English are given below.

Introduction

The modern age is termed as the era of knowledge explosion. This explosion has become possible due to the progress of science and technology. Each and every aspect of human life has changed due to the effects of science and technology. The use of science and technology in the field of communication has revolutionized the whole world. Use of modern technological tools has led to the rise of ICT (Information and Communication technology.) Now ICT is being used in a number of fields like, health, entertainment, games and sports, transportation, education, industries, fashion designing, textiles, agriculture etc. With a single click, we can get exchange a lot of information of the world due to the use of ICT. The field of education is not untouched by the ICT. Now we cannot imagine education without the use of Information and communication Technology. It has made exchange of thoughts, ideas, experiences and feelings easier.

Methods

With the help of ICT a lot of persons can get education and training simultaneously at low cost. Now ICT is being used in all the aspects of education. Use of computers, Internet, television, radio, projectors and mobile phones, e-mail facility, online audio and video conferencing as well as new applications has made the Teaching Learning Process and Training attractive and convenient. It is also helpful in saving time, energy and money. So, we can say that ICT is playing the most important and pivotal role in Teaching Learning Process. Hence it is also playing an important role in the learning of language, especially English Language Learning. Some of the important IT tools and applications used in the field of English Language Teaching are following:
Computers: This is the most important tool of information and communication technology and backbone of modern human life. All the modern communication processes are impossible without the use of computers. It is helpful in storing, preparing, collecting and preparing of

data for communication. It is helpful in the development of listening and speaking skills. It is helpful in English language speaking and listening skills [2].

Overhead projector: It is an important tool of displaying information and processes to a large number of people simultaneously. It can be used in teaching and training of personnel. Prepared forms of information are easy to display with the help of overhead projector.

Lingua phone: This tool is very important in language training of the students. A number of students can practice speaking and hearing drills with the help of lingua phone. It is especially useful in the training of English language listening and speaking skills.

Television: It is useful in education as well as entertainment of the people. It is found that it is helpful in developing listening skills, useful in learning situational language as well as it is highly motivating also. It is very helpful in understanding the language of mass media. A large number of students may be benefitted with the programs of television simultaneously. Many distance and open universities are running their educational programmes on television, such as Indira Gandhi National Open University, Maulana Azad National Urdu University etc. It is an important tool of audio video conferencing. Live telecast of training and discussions are done through this.

Result and Discussion

Internet: It is the most important facility of communication. All the modern communication takes place through this. It has made the communication facility very fast, convenient, economic, and attractive. There are lots of facilities available for communication on internet. Some of them are following:

(a) **Social media:** Social media has become an important tool of communication. It provides a platform for sharing thoughts and ideas. Blogs

are made on it. Students can add themselves with the English language learning groups and take advantage of sharing information. Lots of social sites are available on it like, Face book, Twitter, Instagram etc. It is very helpful in learning situational language.

(b) **Online facilities for English language learning:** A lot of online facilities are available on internet for the development language skills. Some of them are e-guidance, e-tutoring, e-teaching, e-journals, e-magazines, e-books, e-library, online training, virtual classes etc.

(c) **Online language related courses:** These courses are available on internet. Some of them are free and some of them are payable. Students can enroll themselves in these courses and get education and training easily on their own place. Some of the agencies which are providing on line courses are following MOOC, Future Learn, NPTEL, and IITs, Concordia University etc. Students can watch online and offline videos of language learning for the enhancement of their language skills.

(d) **Feature Films in Teaching English:** Films can be used in the teaching of English language. Films may be documentaries, educational and entertainment based. These can arouse high level of motivation. It results in a most satisfying learning experience.

Uses of ICT for an ELT teacher: we cannot think of better educational environment without a better teacher. In earlier times the teacher was the focal point of education, but now the role of teachers has changed a lot. He is considered as a guide and friend of students who helps in learning, does not provides knowledge. To teach better a teacher need to be update with the changes. For this ICT helps a lot. ICT can be useful for a teacher in the following ways.

It is helpful in the professional development of the teachers. A teacher can learn various

language skills with the help of information and communication technologies. He can do various certification programmes in English language teaching run by the famous educational institutions like Cambridge University, British Council etc. These programmes help in enhancing his capacity to teach English language and to make his subject content easy, economic and more understandable.

A teacher can increase his domain of Knowledge English language with the help of e-journals, e-magazines and e-library that can be achieved only through the use of ICT. He can also participate in discussions and conferences with the experts of his English language teaching to improve his knowledge and skills ELT through audio and video conferencing.

ICT helps a teacher to learn innovative methods of teaching. He can work with the students on various project and assignments. It

also helps him in providing teaching contents, home works etc.

He may participate in various in-service training programmes and workshops which are essential for his professional development with the help of information and communication technologies.

ICT helps a teacher to guide his students about the English language learning materials available on internet, e-books, e-journals, e-magazines and social sites like linked-in which are helpful in better learning of English language skills.

In conclusion

ICT also helps him framing curriculum of English language learning. He can study curriculums ELT of different countries to study their pros and cons, challenges as well as sociological and psychological issues related to English language learners. All these things help him in framing a curriculum that leads to achieve the aims and objectives of English language teaching.

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